

Appendix B: Stokes data

In this appendix, we show the Stokes I , Q , U , and V data of the 14 new FRBs with Stokes data dumps, in Fig. B.1. When possible, we have performed an RM measurement, shown in Figures B.2 to B.6.

Table B.1. Apertif Fast Radio Burst polarisation properties.

TNS Name	L/I (%)	$ V /I$ (%)	RM_{obs} (rad m ⁻²)	RM_{MW} (rad m ⁻²)	RM_{host} (rad m ⁻²)
FRB 20191020B	31 ± 7	5 ± 7		24 ± 17	
FRB 20191108A	86 ± 2	0 ± 1	473.1 ± 2.2	-63 ± 13	1400 ⁺³⁰⁰ ₋₅₀₀
FRB 20200213A	10 ± 3	8 ± 6	300.3 ± 2.1	-17 ± 7	1500 ⁺⁴⁰⁰ ₋₅₀₀
FRB 20200216A	38 ± 6	11 ± 4	-2051.0 ± 5.8	-36 ± 10	-4200 ⁺¹³⁰⁰ ₋₈₀₀
FRB 20200321A	17 ± 5	13 ± 9		-16 ± 6	
FRB 20200322A	3 ± 6	14 ± 9		-28 ± 9	
FRB 20200323C	6 ± 3	0 ± 3		-30 ± 6	
FRB 20200419A	77 ± 6	4 ± 6		9 ± 8	
FRB 20200514A	51 ± 5	21 ± 9	979.8 ± 20.5	-215 ± 68	6500 ⁺²⁰⁰⁰ ₋₃₂₀₀
FRB 20200516A	17 ± 13	14 ± 7		1 ± 12	
FRB 20200518A	72 ± 12	29 ± 17		-17 ± 7	
FRB 20201020A	36 ± 2	8 ± 5	125.1 ± 37.5	17 ± 3	200 ⁺¹⁶⁰ ₋₁₄₀
FRB 20210124A	86 ± 8	15 ± 12		32 ± 18	
FRB 20210127A	53 ± 2	4 ± 5	123.5 ± 0.4	35 ± 9	340 ⁺¹³⁰ ₋₁₆₀
FRB 20210317A	50 ± 5	3 ± 4	-251.7 ± 1.3	26 ± 20	-530 ⁺¹⁶⁰ ₋₁₃₀
FRB 20210530A	52 ± 4	0 ± 7	-125.1 ± 4.6	-37 ± 10	-390 ⁺¹⁹⁰ ₋₁₆₀

Notes. Only FRBs with triggered full-Stokes data dumps are listed here. To ensure uniform layout, insignificant digits are sometimes also included.

Fig. B.1. Stokes IQUV data of triggered FRBs. Each top panel shows the pulse profile of total intensity (Stokes I - black), linear polarisation ($\sqrt{Q^2 + U^2}$ - blue) after Faraday de-rotation when an RM is known, and circular polarisation (Stokes V - orange). The bottom panels show respectively Stokes I, Q, U, and V, without Faraday de-rotation. Blue indicates a positive value and red a negative value. The FRB name is indicated on the top right corner.

Fig. B.1. (Continued)

Fig. B.2. Rotation measure analysis of FRB 20200213A. The frequency channels between 1291 and 1436 MHz were used for the RM synthesis, since they are contained within the full width at tenth maximum of the spectrum fitted to a Gaussian.

Fig. B.3. Rotation measure analysis of FRB 20200514A. The whole bandwidth was used.

Fig. B.4. Rotation measure analysis of FRB 20210127A. The whole bandwidth was used.

Fig. B.5. Rotation measure analysis of FRB 20210317A. The whole bandwidth was used.

Fig. B.6. Rotation measure analysis of FRB 20210530A. The whole bandwidth was used.

Appendix C: Extended Analysis, Results and Discussion

Appendix C.1: Faraday rotation measure analysis

The RM (rad m⁻²) measures the integrated strength of the magnetic field parallel to the line of sight along the propagation path (e.g. Petroff et al. 2019). In the case of a source located at a redshift $z = z_{\text{src}}$, the RM can be expressed as (Mckinven et al. 2021):

$$\text{RM} = -C_R \int_0^{z_{\text{src}}} \frac{n_e(z) B_{\parallel}(z)}{(1+z)^2} \frac{dl}{dz} dz, \quad (\text{C.1})$$

with $C_R = 811.9 \text{ rad m}^{-2}/(\mu\text{G pc cm}^{-3})$, n_e the free electron density along the line of sight, B_{\parallel} the magnetic field strength parallel to the propagation path, and $dl(z)$ the distance element along the line of sight at redshift z .

The RM is observed as oscillations in the Q and U intensities, periodic on λ^2 , with λ the observed wavelength in metres. For FRBs where we observe oscillations in the Q and U intensities, we apply the RM synthesis method to estimate the Faraday rotation (see Burn 1966; Brentjens & Bruyn 2005). This technique applies the equivalent of a Fourier transformation to the complex linear polarisation, $P(\lambda^2) = Q(\lambda^2) + iU(\lambda^2)$, though this expression only has a physical meaning for $\lambda^2 \geq 0$;

$$F(\phi) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(\lambda^2) e^{-2i\phi\lambda^2} d\lambda^2, \quad (\text{C.2})$$

where $|F(\phi)|$ is the total linearly polarised intensity within the observed bandwidth after Faraday de-rotating $P(\lambda^2)$ by the Faraday depth ϕ (rad m⁻²). The complex linear polarisation can also be written as $P(\lambda^2) = |P|e^{2i\psi}$, with the PPA $\psi(\lambda^2) = \psi_0 + \text{RM}\lambda^2$, and ψ_0 the polarisation position angle at a reference frequency. A Faraday dispersion function (FDF) is built by computing $F(\phi)$ at different ϕ and ψ trial values, and the RM and ψ_0 are given by the (ϕ, ψ) values that maximise the FDF. To determine the best RM value and errors, we fit the FDF peak to a parabolic curve.

Once the (RM, ψ_0) solution has been found, the Stokes Q and U can be Faraday de-rotated, and the resulting $L/I = \sqrt{Q^2 + U^2}/I$ will give us the linear polarisation fraction. The circular polarisation fraction will in turn be given by V/I . The PPA can be expressed as a function of time t and frequency ν as follows:

$$\psi(t, \nu) = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{U(t, \nu)}{Q(t, \nu)}. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

After Faraday de-rotating Stokes Q and U , we can study the PPA evolution with time. This PPA is given by the polarisation angle of the emission at the source, and it is thus a property intrinsic to the FRB. It is set by the properties of the magnetic field in the emission regions, since the plane of the linear polarisation coincides with the local plane of curvature of the magnetic field lines. This holds true both for pulsar-like and synchrotron maser emission mechanisms.

Appendix C.2: Scattering of FRB 20200210A

To better characterise the scattering of FRB 20200210A, we used `scatfit` to divide the full bandwidth into 8 subbands, and computed the S/N of the FRB in each one. If the S/N was above a threshold of 4.5, we performed a scattering fit. We used the scattering timescales in each subband to fit them to a power law as a function of frequency, since we expect $\tau_{\text{sc}} \propto \nu^{-\alpha}$. We find

a scattering index $\alpha = 13.8 \pm 0.9$ (Note that `scatfit` defines the scattering index with an opposite sign). This result is robust, since we find a consistent α value when changing the number of frequency subbands to 16 and use a different S/N threshold. If this scattering index is used to scale the scattering timescale to 1 GHz, it would result in $\tau_{\text{sc}} \sim 1700 \pm 700$ ms. The result is shown in Fig. C.1.

Fig. C.1. Multi-frequency scattering fit result for FRB 20200210A. The top panel shows the pulse profile in 6 subbands with S/N>4.5, each one fitted to a Gaussian convolved with an exponential decay. The bottom panel shows the fit result at each subband. The scattering timescales are shown as crosses, while the fit to a scattering index is shown as a solid line. The text at the top right corner gives the expected scattering timescale at 1 GHz given the spectral index, and the line below the scattering index α .

Appendix C.3: Foreground galaxy clusters of FRB 20200719A

Fig. C.2. Foreground galaxy clusters around the localisation of FRB 20200719A. The FRB localisation is indicated by a pink ellipse, while the clusters are represented by circles ranging from blue to white with increasing redshift. The size of the circles shows the R_{500} radius (Zou et al. 2021). The background image is from Pan-STARRS.

Appendix C.4: Scattering

Fig. C.3. Scattering index as a function of scattering timescale, for the applicable Apertif FRBs (black markers). The golden and blue dashed horizontal line indicate scattering indices of 4 (as expected for a thin screen), and 4.4 (for Kolmogorov turbulence) respectively.

Appendix C.5: Dispersion

Fig. C.4. Distribution of Apertif FRB DMs compared to other FRB samples. The top panels show DMs as observed (left) and the excess given the Milky Way contribution (right), with Apertif in green, CHIME/FRB in orange, and all other FRBs in the TNS in black. The bottom panels show the respective cumulative distributions, now for the single-instrument samples marked in the legend.